

THE DECOMPOSITION OF VECTOR FUNCTIONS IN VECTOR-MATRIX SERIES INTO STATE-SPACE OF NONLINEAR DYNAMIC SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Decomposition relationships for nonlinear dynamic system operators into state-space based on vector-matrix series are proposed. The representation for a shift operator on trajectories of nonlinear dynamic system through shift operators on trajectories of multidimensional linear dynamic systems was obtained.

Keywords: nonlinear dynamic systems, state-space, vector-matrix series, shift operator on the trajectories

1 INTRODUCTION

Decomposition methods of nonlinear operators describing the behavior of system in state-space (phase-space) are very actual and important for analysis, identification and modeling of nonlinear dynamic systems (NDS), in particular NDS with self-organization (or complex systems). In connection with this the aim of this paper is deduction and classification of vector-matrix series describing decomposition of vector functions from phase-space variables, shift operators trajectories of nonlinear differential equations and NDS operators in the state-space.

2 THE DECOMPOSITION RELATIONSHIPS FOR VECTOR FUNCTIONS INTO VECTOR-MATRIX SERIES

The mechanisms of occurrence of spatial and temporary structures in complex NDS can be revealed from the analysis of system of the nonlinear equations in partial derivative as follows [1]:

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} = f_i(\{u_j\}, \{\nabla u_j\}, \{\nabla^2 u_j\}, \dots, x(t)), \quad i, j = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

where f_i is a nonlinear function, and $u_i = u_i(t, \vec{r})$ is a function of a temporary t and a spatial $\vec{r}$ variables satisfying to the initial conditions, ∇ is differential Hamilton operator. Further we will not take into account obvious dependence u_i on a spatial vector $\vec{r}$, i.e. $u_i = u_i(t)$. In a vector-matrix form the system of the equations (1) can be written down as follows:

$$\frac{d\vec{u}}{dt} = \vec{f}(\vec{u}^T(t), x(t), \vec{u}_0), \quad \vec{u}(0) = \vec{u}_0, \quad \vec{u}(t) \in R^N, \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{u}^T(t) = (u_1(t), \dots, u_N(t))$, T is a transposition symbol, $\vec{u}_0$ is a vector of the initial data. The decision $\vec{u}(t)$ of the equation (2) gives a some curve in state-space (phase space) $U = R^N$ called as a phase trajectory.

It is often necessary to study behavior of the decision of the equation (1) near to a specific standard state $\{u_i^*, u_i^* = u_i^*(t)\}$ being considered as the undisturbed decision (1), permanently: disturbed by external actions or internal fluctuations on size $v_i = v_i(t)$ [1]. In result instead of u_i^* a new decision becomes

$$u_i = u_i^* + v_i. \quad (3)$$

From relations (1) and (3) we will receive system of the equations for $\{v_i\}$:

$$\frac{dv_i}{dt} = f_i(u_j^* + v_j) - f_i(u_j^*). \quad (4)$$

Near to a reference time, i.e. at $|v_i/u_i^*| \ll 1$,

we can linearize function f_i near to zero values $v_j = 0$ using the first terms of a multiple Taylor series [1]:

$$\Delta f_i(\{v_j\}) = f_i(\{u_j^* + v_j\}) - f_i(\{u_j^*\}) \approx \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v_j} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} v_j. \quad (5)$$

With the account of (4) the relation (5) will be given as

$$\frac{dv_i}{dt} \approx \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v_j} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} v_j. \quad (6)$$

This relation represents a linearized (or variational) system of the equations [1]. The Lyapunov theorem establishes connection between stability of systems of the equations (1) and (6): if the trivial decision ($v_j=0$) of equation (6) is asymptotically steady then u_j^* is asymptotically steady decision of the equation (1). The system of the differential equations (6) can be written down in a vector-matrix form using the linearized matrix operator $L_{N \times N}^{(1)} = [L_{ij}^{(1)}]$, where

$$L_{ij}^{(1)} = \frac{\partial f_i(0)}{\partial v_j}, \quad i, j=1, \dots, N.$$

Then we will obtain

$$\frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} \approx L_{N \times N}^{(1)} \vec{v}, \quad (7)$$

where $\vec{v}$ is a column-vector with components $v_1, \dots, v_N$, $L_{N \times N}$ is a square matrix ($N \times N$) of derivative values of the first orders for vector function.

To write down system of the nonlinear differential equations for a deviation from a standard state in a vector-matrix form, one uses a decomposition of vector function $\Delta f_i(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_N)$ in a multiple Taylor series in view of the assumption (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f_i(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_N) &= f_i(u_1^* + v_1, u_2^* + v_2, \dots, u_N^* + v_N) - \\ &- f_i(u_1^*, u_2^*, \dots, u_N^*) = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v_j} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} \cdot v_j + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{j=k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial^2 f_i}{\partial v_j \partial v_k} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} \cdot v_j \cdot v_k + \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{j=k=l=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial^3 f_i}{\partial v_j \partial v_k \partial v_l} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} \cdot v_j \cdot v_k \cdot v_l + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Similarly (7) one writes down (8) in vector-matrix notation. With this purpose a kernel of the linear term in decomposition (8) is presented as follows:

$$L_{ij}^{(1)} = \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v_j} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_j} \cdot f_i \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)}. \quad (9)$$

In accordance with (9) each element of the matrix operator $L_{N \times N}^{(1)}$ is formed by a formal multiplication of row-vector elements of the differential operators $\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial}{\partial v_N} \right)$ and column-vector ones of functions $\vec{f} = (f_1, \dots, f_N)^T$. It means, that the matrix $L_{N \times N}^{(1)}$ can be represented as Kronecker product [2] of row-vector $\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T}$ of order $1 \times N$ and column-vector $\vec{f}$ of order $N \times 1$

calculated in a point $\vec{v}^T = (0, \dots, 0) = \vec{o}^T$:

$$L_{N \times N}^{(1)} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \vec{f} \right)_{\vec{o}^T} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_1} \vec{f} \right)_0 \dots \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_N} \vec{f} \right)_0 \right], \quad (10)$$

where $\otimes$ is a symbol of Kronecker matrix product.

Similarly one writes down the kernel of the quadratic term in the decomposition (8) as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 f_i}{\partial v_j \partial v_k} \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_j} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v_k} \cdot f_i \right) \right)_{(0, \dots, 0)}. \quad (11)$$

The matrix whose elements are formed according to a rule (11) is written down as Kronecker product of three vectors calculated at $\vec{v}^T = \vec{o}^T$:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \vec{f} \right) \right)_{\vec{o}^T} = L_{N \times N^2}^{(2)}. \quad (12)$$

Let's notice, that according to construction (12) the matrix $L_{N \times N^2}^{(2)}$ is rectangular one of order $(N \times N^2)$ coordinated with a column-vector of order $(N^2 \times 1)$ as a form $(\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v})$ whose elements are $v_j v_k$ according to the quadratic term in decomposition (8). Then the system of the equations (4) written down as vector-matrix form in view of the quadratic term from (8) can be approximated as follows [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} &\approx L_{N \times N}^{(1)} \vec{v} + \frac{1}{2!} L_{N \times N^2}^{(2)} (\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) = \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \vec{f} \right)_{\vec{o}^T} \vec{v} + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \vec{f} \right) \right)_{\vec{o}^T} (\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

It is clear that (13) can be generalized for a case of approximation $\frac{d\vec{v}}{dt}$ by the terms of the higher orders.

With the account (4) and (13) it is easy to see, that a change of vector function in state-space is decomposed in a vector-matrix series [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \vec{f}(\vec{v}^T) &= \vec{f}(\vec{u}^{*T} + \vec{v}^T) - \vec{f}(\vec{u}^{*T}) = L_{N \times N}^{(1)} \vec{v} + \frac{1}{2!} L_{N \times N^2}^{(2)} (\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} L_{N \times N^3}^{(3)} (\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) + \dots = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} L_{N \times N^k}^{(k)} \cdot \vec{v}^{\otimes k}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $L_{N \times N^k}^{(k)} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \dots \otimes \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^T} \otimes \vec{f} \right) \dots \right) \right)_{\vec{o}^T}$ are matrix kernels of the homogeneous nonlinear operators of system in state-space $\vec{v}^{\otimes k} = \underbrace{(\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v} \otimes \dots \otimes \vec{v})}_k$ is k^{th} Kronecker degree of a vector $\vec{v}$. The relation (14) describes the *first form* of vector-matrix decomposition.

In accordance with the (3) $\vec{u} = \vec{u}^* + \vec{v}$. In view of this one rewrites the relation (14) as follows [2]:

$$\vec{f}(\vec{u}^T) = \vec{f}(\vec{u}^{*T}) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} L_{N \times N^k}^{(k)} \cdot (\vec{u} - \vec{u}^*)^{\otimes k}. \quad (15)$$

It is clear that the relation (20) describes a decomposition of a vector function $\vec{f}$ near to a vector of the initial data $\vec{u}^*$ (or the vector of a standard state of system) in a vector-matrix series.

There is one more vector-matrix form [2] of a multiple Taylor series, which can be received from (8) if we suppose that independent variables $v_j, v_k, v_l, \dots$ are values of the function $v(t)$ into the various moments of time accordingly $\tau_j, \tau_k, \tau_l, \dots$, i.e. $v_j = v(\tau_j), v_k = v(\tau_k), v_l = v(\tau_l), \dots$. In other words the vector $\vec{v}(t)$ into state-space may be described by a sequences of linear-independent vectors $\vec{v}(\tau_j), \vec{v}(\tau_k), \vec{v}(\tau_l), \dots$ in the various moments of time $t = \tau_j, \tau_k, \tau_l, \dots$. Considering this fact and

notation (9) kernel of the linear term in decomposition (8) is written as follows [2]:

$$L_i^{(1)}(\tau_j) = \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v(\tau_j)} \right)_{(v^*(\tau_1), \dots, v^*(\tau_N))} = \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial v_j(\tau)} \right)_{(v_1^*(\tau), \dots, v_N^*(\tau))} = L_{ij}(\tau) \quad (16)$$

i.e. the correspondent matrix to (16) is $L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau)$.

Using (16) the vector-matrix decomposition (14) may be represented in the *second form* [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \vec{f}(\vec{v}^T) &= L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) \vec{v}(\tau_1) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \vec{v}(\tau_1) \vec{v}(\tau_2) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} L_{N \times N}^{(3)}(\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3) \vec{v}(\tau_1) \vec{v}(\tau_2) \vec{v}(\tau_3) + \dots = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} L_{N \times N}^{(k)}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_k) \prod_{i=1}^k \vec{v}(\tau_i). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

It is easy to see that series (14) one-to-one transforms in series (17) by the following bijective maps:

$$\alpha: L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau) \cdot (\vec{v}(\tau) \otimes \vec{v}(\tau)) \rightarrow L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \vec{v}(\tau_1) \vec{v}(\tau_2);$$

$$\beta: L_{N \times N}^{(3)}(\tau) \cdot (\vec{v}(\tau) \otimes \vec{v}(\tau) \otimes \vec{v}(\tau)) \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow L_{N \times N}^{(3)}(\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3) \vec{v}(\tau_1) \vec{v}(\tau_2) \vec{v}(\tau_3); \dots;$$

$$\omega: L_{N \times N}^{(k)}(\tau) \vec{v}^{\otimes k} \rightarrow L_{N \times N}^{(k)}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_k) \prod_{i=1}^k \vec{v}(\tau_i). \quad (18)$$

3 THE SHIFT OPERATORS ON THE TRAJECTORIES OF ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

It is shown in [3] that the linearized vector equation (7) decision (satisfying to the initial condition $\vec{v}(0) = \vec{v}_0$) can be written down as:

$$\vec{v}(t) = V_{N \times N}(t) \vec{v}_0, \quad (19)$$

where the operator-function $V(t)$ is determined by the Peano series [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{N \times N}(t) &= E_{N \times N} + \int_0^t L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 + \\ &+ \int_0^t L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_2) \int_0^{\tau_2} L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \dots + \\ &+ \int_0^t L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_k) \int_0^{\tau_k} L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_{k-1}) \dots \int_0^{\tau_2} L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 \dots d\tau_k + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

(here $E_{N \times N}$ is an unit matrix). The operator-function $V_{N \times N}(t)$ is an *shift operator* on trajectories of *linear dynamic system* (LDS) (7). On the other hand in [3] it is shown that the operator $V_{N \times N}(t)$ is the Frechét derivative of the shift operator $\vec{u}(t) = \vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}_0^T)$ on trajectories of system (2) in a point $\vec{u}^*$:

$$\vec{p}'_{\vec{u}}(t; 0, \vec{u}^{*T}) = V_{N \times N}(t), \quad (21)$$

i.e. shift operator on trajectories of LDS is the Frechét derivative of the shift operator on trajectories of NDS.

Differentiating on t both parts (21) and taking into account (2) one receives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} V_{N \times N}(t) &= \frac{d}{dt} \vec{p}'_{\vec{u}}(t; 0, \vec{u}^{*T}) = \\ &= \left(\frac{d}{dt} \vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}^{*T}) \right)'_{\vec{u}} = \vec{f}'_{\vec{u}}(t, \vec{u}^{*T}). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Taking into account (20) one writes down a relation (22) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{f}'_{\vec{u}}(t, \vec{u}^{*T}) &= L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) (E_{N \times N} + \int_0^t L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 + \\ &+ \int_0^t L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) \int_0^{\tau_1} L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_2) d\tau_2 d\tau_1 + \dots) = \\ &= L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) \cdot V_{N \times N}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

from here

$$\vec{f}'_{\vec{u}}(t, \vec{u}^{*T}) \vec{v}_0 = L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) V(t) \vec{v}_0. \quad (24)$$

Considering that $\|\vec{v}_0\| \rightarrow 0$ and also taking into account definition by the Frechét derivative [3] one receives

$$\vec{f}'_{\vec{u}}(t, \vec{u}^{*T}) \vec{v}_0 \rightarrow \vec{f}(t, \vec{u}^{*T} + \vec{v}_0^T) - \vec{f}(t, \vec{u}^{*T}) = \Delta \vec{f}(\vec{v}_0^T). \quad (25)$$

In accordance with (19) the right part (24) accepts the form

$$L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) V_{N \times N}(t) \vec{v}_0 = L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) \vec{v}(t). \quad (26)$$

Transforming the left part of (24) according to (25) and the right part of (24) according to (26) one receives

$$\Delta \vec{f}(\vec{v}_0) \rightarrow L_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) \vec{v}(t), \text{ if } \|\vec{v}_0\| \rightarrow 0. \quad (27)$$

Obviciously, the relation (27) is the special case of (17) describing the formula of linearization of NDS.

4 THE DECOMPOSITION OF SHIFT OPERATOR ON THE TRAJECTORIES INTO STATE-SPACE OF NDS

Obeying the obtained decompositions (14), (15), (17) we shall describe algebraic structure of NDS into state-space. Considering that input NDS signal $x(t)$ is continuous everywhere on a real axis the output signal $y(t)$ from this NDS is represented on the basis of the convergent functional Volterra series [4]:

$$y(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} H_m[x(t)], \quad (28)$$

$$H_m[x(t)] = \int_0^{\infty} \dots \int_0^{\infty} h_m(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m) \prod_{i=1}^m x(t - \tau_i) d\tau_i, \quad (29)$$

where $H_m[x(t)]$ is the homogeneous operators of a degree m . The sum of M homogeneous operators $H_m[x(t)]$ is called as a *functional polynomial* of a degree M :

$$P_M[x] = \sum_{m=0}^M H_m[x(t)]. \quad (30)$$

In the case when $m=1$ the functional Volterra series (28) is reduced to an equation of convolution describing a LDS, and the kernel $h_1(\tau_1)$ is accordingly called impulse response for LDS. According to R. Kalman [6] for one-

dimensional *stationary* LDS the impulse response based on a state-space method can be represented as

$$h(t) = \begin{cases} H_{I \times N} e^{L_{N \times N} t} G_{N \times I}, & \text{if } t \geq 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } t < 0, \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where $H_{I \times N}$ and $G_{N \times I}$ are matrices generating over real field $\mathbb{R}$ accordingly homomorphisms: $G: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow U$; $H: U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $L_{N \times N}$ is the matrix generating a cyclic vector space $C_L[\vec{u}_0]$ being a state-space for stationary LDS: $L_{N \times N}: U \rightarrow U$ [5], [6]. Let us note that for stationary LDS the ratio is valid [6]:

$$V_{N \times N}(t) = e^{L_{N \times N} t}, \quad (32)$$

where $V_{N \times N}(t)$ is the shift operator on trajectories of stationary LDS. Therefore, taking into account (32) formula (31) has the form

$$h(t) = \begin{cases} H_{I \times N} V_{N \times N}(t) G_{N \times I}, & \text{if } t \geq 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } t < 0. \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

According to (33) the first term (27) in matrix - vector series (17) into state space of LDS generates the first term in functional Volterra series (28) describing one-dimensional LDS into space of inputs - output signals for the given NDS:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1[x(t)] &= \int_0^\infty H_{I \times N} V_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) G_{N \times I} x(t - \tau_1) d\tau_1 = \\ &= \int_0^\infty H_{I \times N} V_{N \times N}^{(1)}(\tau_1) \vec{u}(t - \tau_1) d\tau_1, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where $\vec{u}(t) = G_{N \times I}^{(1)} x(t)$ is the vector into the state space. Analogously the second term in the matrix-vector series (17)

$$\vec{f}_2(t, t', \vec{u}^T) = L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(t, t') \vec{u}(t) \vec{u}(t'), \quad (35)$$

generates the second term in the functional Volterra series (28) describing two-dimensional separable LDS:

$$H_2[x(t)] = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty H_{I \times N} V_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \vec{u}(t - \tau_1) \vec{u}(t - \tau_2) d\tau_1 d\tau_2, \quad (36)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} V_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau_1, \tau_2) &= E_{N \times N} + \int_0^{\tau_1} \int_0^{\tau_2} L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(t, t') dt dt' + \\ &+ \int_0^{\tau_1} \int_0^{\tau_2} L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(\tau'_1, \tau'_2) \int_0^{\tau_1} \int_0^{\tau_2} L_{N \times N}^{(2)}(t, t') d\tau'_1 d\tau'_2 dt dt' + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

i.e. the shift operator on trajectories of two-dimensional LDS.

On the other hand, according to the Frechét derivative (21) of the shift operator on trajectories of NDS the expression is valid

$$\vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}^T) = V_{N \times N}(t) \vec{u} + \vec{\varepsilon}(\vec{u}^T), \quad (38)$$

if $\vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}^{*T}) = 0$ and $\vec{u}^* = \vec{0}$. Generalizing (38) it is easy to see that

$$\vec{p}_{\vec{u}}(t_1, t_2; 0, \vec{u}^T) = V_{N \times N}^{(2)}(t_1, t_2) \vec{u}(t_1) \vec{u}(t_2) + \vec{\varepsilon}_2(\vec{u}^T). \quad (39)$$

The k-order homogeneous operators may be found by a generalization of (38), (39),..., i.e. according to

$$\vec{p}(t_1, \dots, t_k, \vec{u}^T) = V_{N \times N}^{(k)}(t_1, \dots, t_k) \prod_{i=1}^k \vec{u}(t_i). \quad (40)$$

Taking into account the bijective maps (18) the relation (40) may be rewritten as

$$\vec{p}_k(t, \vec{u}^T) = V_{N \times N}^{(k)}(t) \vec{u}^{\otimes k}. \quad (41)$$

According to [3] the shift operator on the trajectories of NDS under condition of its k times differentiable in Frechét sense can be represented as the following:

$$\vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}^T) = \vec{p}_1(t, \vec{u}^T) + \frac{1}{2!} \vec{p}_2(t, \vec{u}^T) + \dots + \frac{1}{k!} \vec{p}_k(t, \vec{u}^T) + \dots \quad (42)$$

if $\vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{0}^T) = \vec{0}$. By substituting (41) into (42) we obtain the representation for a shift operator on trajectories of NDS through shift operators on trajectories of k-dimensional LDS [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{p}(t; 0, \vec{u}^T) &= V_{N \times N}^{(1)}(t) \vec{u} + \frac{1}{2!} V_{N \times N}^{(2)}(t) (\vec{u} \otimes \vec{u}) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} V_{N \times N}^{(3)}(t) (\vec{u} \otimes \vec{u} \otimes \vec{u}) + \dots + \frac{1}{k!} V_{N \times N}^{(k)}(t) \vec{u}^{\otimes k} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

The decomposition (43) as well as (14), (17) ones permit us to calculate of characteristic parameters of complex NDS (for example, minimal attractor embedding dimension of chaotic NDS [7] etc.).

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